

ARCHAEOLOGICAL GEOPHYSICAL SURVEY OF THE DIONISIO POINT SITE, DgRv-3

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INTRODUCTION

From May 19 through 27, 2014, the Center for advanced Spatial Technologies (CAST) at the University of Arkansas conducted a geophysical survey of the Dionisio Point Site, DgRv-3, in the Southern Gulf Islands of British Columbia. The survey was supported by Spatial Archaeometry Research Collaborations (SPARC) award for Washington State University (WSU). The SPARC Program is based at CAST at the University of Arkansas, and is funded by a generous grant from the National Science Foundation (Award #1321443).

DIONISIO POINT SITE

DgRv-3 is a Marpole phase village site (1700-1400 BP) within the Dionisio Point Provincial Park on Galiano Island, BC (Grier 2001). The site consists of five plank house depressions that form a terraced landscape on a northern inlet coast of the island. Three terraces, containing 4 of the 5 house depressions (Houses 2-5), are separated by elevations of 2 to 3 meters, while the lowest and most remote house (House 1) is situated just above a gravel beach to the northeast. Shell middens form the built-up ridges surrounding the house perimeters (Grier 2003).

The site currently is surrounded by a wooden fence that guides hikers visiting the park along the southern edge of the site and away from the house depressions. The prehistoric village has been excavated since 1997 under the direction of Colin Grier. Intensive excavations have covered just under 40% of the interior area of House 2. House 5 was also excavated but to a lesser extent. The intensive excavations of house 2 have produced information regarding local fishing and storage practices that tie into economic and social networks of the area (Grier 2003).

Previous ground penetrating radar studies was performed at DgRv-3 by Lisa Dojack at University of British Columbia (UBC). The survey was conducted with success in locating below surface features that have been field verified (Dojack 2011 and 2012). Additional Magnetic and Electric Surveys were requested by WSU in order to understand the overall spatial distribution of interior house features at the site.

During this project magnetic gradiometry was performed over Houses 1, and 3 through 5. House 2 was not surveyed due to magnetic interference from metal and the extensive excavations. An additional small grid (Grid 1) was surveyed along the high midden deposit ridge to the east. Electromagnetic surveys were also run on small areas of Houses 1, 3 and 5.

THEORY AND INSTRUMENTATION

Geophysical concepts have been successfully utilized on a variety of archaeological sites. This success is dependent on the soil properties that make up the archaeological context, and the contrasting properties of the archaeology to that soil (Bevan 1983; Kvamme 2001). Contrast between the archaeology and the surrounding soil is enhanced through anthropogenic processes, or human activity. Different activities naturally create different geophysical characteristics in the soil that can ultimately be detected with geophysical instruments. Each method of geophysical prospection is unique in what it delineates as an anomaly. This project utilized magnetic gradiometry, electrical conductivity and magnetic susceptibility. The following discussion is of the three geophysical applications to archaeology.

Magnetic Gradiometry

Magnetic gradiometers passively measure the local magnetic field below them at a given location; in contrast, the active sensors of magnetic susceptibility meters generate their own artificial fields to measure the ability of a given material to become magnetized. The gradiometer's reading is a measure of the sum of both induced and remnant magnetizations (Dalan 2005).

Remanent magnetism is the permanent magnetization of a material that occurs during its compositional, thermal or depositional history (Heimmer and De Vore 1995). These materials remain magnetic in the absence of a magnetic field. Magnetometry surveys can be particularly successful in detecting anthropogenic activities that utilize or create materials with remanent magnetism. The success is partially due to the remanent magnetism of thermoremanent materials that often appear as robust anomalies in magnetic data. Thermoremanence occurs when soils, clays or rocks containing iron oxides are heated—most naturally contain 1 to 10 percent. The particles at first have no net magnetic properties, but when heated to the Curie point (about 600° C) the magnetization is completely removed only to remagnetize at the time of cooling to the current geomagnetic field (Clark 2001). Many processes of heating were common in prehistoric and historic settlements including pottery production, cooking and perhaps the destruction of structures through burning (Kvamme 2006).

The earth's magnetic field produces a second type of magnetism known as induced magnetism. This type of magnetism only exists in the presence of a magnetic field. The potential of a material to become magnetized is known as its magnetic susceptibility, which is a function of the minerals in its composition that can become magnetized. Most soils and rocks contain such minerals and, in general, topsoils tend to be more magnetically susceptible than subsoil layers as well the rocks they were produced from. This is the case for several reasons including anthropogenic and naturally occurring fires as well as human refuse of organic and thermally altered materials during occupation. There is also a natural tendency for iron minerals to accumulate in topsoil due to their relative insolubility in comparison less magnetic soil contents. Additionally, pedogenic enhancements such as low-heat chemical reactions as well as organic processes such as magnetotactic bacteria and other bacteria that cause the magnetic compounds to accumulate in topsoils (Dalan 2005, Kvamme 2006).

Slight anthropogenic alterations to topsoils are therefore detectable using sensitive instruments like magnetometers and magnetic susceptibility meters. The magnetic gradiometer has two sensors aligned vertically. The difference between the two measurements is called the "magnetic field gradient" (Kvamme 2001) and the unit of measurement for magnetic surveys is the nanotesla (nT). The use of the two sensors makes for a quick yet sensitive survey instrument. The distance of sensor separation determines the sensitivity of the instrument. The farther the sensors are apart the closer it approaches the sensitivity of a total field measurement. However, there is a limit to how far apart the sensors can be with confidence that the operator can maintain vertical alignment while walking a straight line; a standard distance is .5 to 1 m (Clark 2001).

Electromagnetic Conductivity and Magnetic Susceptibility

Electromagnetic (EM) surveys actively measure soil properties by inducing a phenomenon through a radio transmitter. The transmitter induces an electromagnetic field that generates eddy currents in conductive materials. A secondary electro-magnetic field proportional to soil conductivity is produced and then measured by a receiver coil (Bevan 1998; Kvamme 2003). The depth of prospection is determined by the distance between coils and the frequency emitted. The EM instrument used most often in archaeological surveys measure both the conductivity (quad-phase) and magnetic susceptibility (in-phase) of the soil.

Conductivity is measured as millisiemens per meter (mS/m). Soils conductive properties vary. A soil composed of sand and gravels will have a relatively low conductivity (0.1-1 mS/m) in comparison to a clay soil (25-100 mS/m). When archaeological features involve the movement of these soils the contrast can be picked up by the EM instrument (Bevan 1998). It is notable that conductivity is the inverse of resistivity as measured by a resistance meter.

Magnetic susceptibility is measured in the presence of the magnetized field. Magnetic susceptibility or χ (ppt) is dependent on the type and amount of material present. As discussed above, magnetic susceptibility measures the ability of a material to be magnetized. Unlike the magnetic gradiometer which measures the sum of remanent magnetism as well as magnetic susceptibility, a magnetic susceptibility meter solely measures the latter.

GEOPHYSICAL SURVEY AT DgRv-3

Field Methods

Prior to the survey a metal detector was used to locate known metal objects across the site. Many previous excavation unit corners still contained metal nails. Each nail that was relocated was removed from the survey area. Other shallow surface metal debris was also removed when found with the metal detector and documented on hand-drawn field maps for each grid.

Three grids varying in sizes were identified and staked out using a Nikon DTM-520 total station provided by WSU. One continuous grid measuring 37 m E-W x 40 m N-S was surveyed over Houses 3, 4 and 5. The terraced houses created steep terrain and many trees and logs formed obstacles for the instruments and surveyors. The gradiometer was reconfigured to use one sensor. This alleviated the need to stop at every obstacle and restart measurements. It also contributed to the time it took to survey each grid. The area was surveyed with the magnetometer with 0.5 m transect spacing guided by fiberglass tapes laid precisely along the transect direction. Eight samples were recorded per meter (0.125). A separate grid was surveyed over House 1 at a 0.25 m transect intervals with eight samples per meter for both magnetic and EM surveys. Grid 1 over the midden area to the east was surveyed solely with the magnetometer at 0.5 m transect spacing and 8 samples per meter.

A Bartington 601 Magnetic Gradiometer was employed in this survey. It is a single axis magnetic field gradiometer system comprised of two gradiometers mounted 0.5 meters apart on a horizontal carrying bar. Each gradiometer contains magnetometry sensors vertically spaced 0.5 meters. This instruments configuration provides sensitivity of archaeological anomalies to an average depth of one meter. This instrument is designed for archaeological prospection and allows geophysical surveys to be completed rapidly relative to other geophysical methods. However, due to the scale and prolific presence of obstacles at Dionisio Point, a single sensor configuration was used.

A Geonics EM38B was the electromagnetic conductivity and magnetic susceptibility meter (EM) used in this survey. It has a coil distance of 1 m reaching approximately 0.5 m in depth provides depths of exploration at 1.5 meters and 0.75 meters in the vertical and horizontal dipole modes respectively. Measurements are made by placing this instrument on the ground and recording the meter reading. Digital meters are located on the top and the side of the EM38 for the horizontal and vertical dipole measurements.

After the initial survey, areas of interest were identified and smaller areas within the house platforms were chosen for higher resolution surveys. A 0.25 m transect spacing was conducted in these areas as well as an EM survey at the same resolution. .

GPS Mapping

A Trimble XH Global Position System unit was used to record 3 known positions on or near the site. These GPS coordinates will aid in georeferencing the site total station data collected in a local grid to real world coordinates. Between the three locations over 16,000 points were collected ensuring high accuracy despite dense tree cover at the site.

Data Processing

The surveys were performed under the guideline that careful data collection in the field will result in less data manipulation during data processing, a major goal in geophysical prospection in archaeology. The Gradiometer and EM instruments were downloaded and processed in ArchaeoFusion, a program developed by CAST. Magnetic data was clipped to within two standard deviations of the mean. To remove instrument drift, a zero mean traverse function was applied. This process makes the average of each line surveyed equal to zero, the theoretical value of a uniform background without gradient. Often another clip was applied once the mean is at zero.

As discussed above, depending on the instrument, the topography and the desired goal, data were collected at different sample intervals and transect spacing. Resampling or interpolating the data added estimated values based on known data values resulting in a uniform sample cell interval. Final processing techniques involved the use of a low pass filters to smooth details. Geophysical results were exported to .tiff file formats for interpretations in ArcGIS 10.2. Interpretations were created as shapefiles. GPS data were post-processed using Pathfinder Office 5.2. Using 6 reference stations both carrier and code phase data corrections provided sub-meter accuracy (50% at 0-15cm).

RESULTS

The data collected at the site was successful in displaying clear distinctions between interior and exterior anomalies. Appendix A contains all Results maps. **Figure A1** shows the magnetic gradiometry data with a grey-scale color ramp. In this image black equals highly magnetic data and white equals low magnetic data. The values are clipped to +/- 30 nT. The data range relatively great for archaeological features in North America, however the rich organic materials of the Pacific Northwest and geology of the island could account for high magnetic values. Null or Dummy values due to vegetation are also white, but can be identified as missing strips of data where the instrument was stopped and restarted due to trees or obstacles. **Figures A2** and **A3** isolate the high magnetic anomalies (>0 nT) and low magnetic anomalies (<0 nT) respectively. General observations in the isolated high magnetic image include discrete high magnetic anomalies that are clearly isolated within house depressions. More amorphous high anomalies are seen between houses and are consistent with midden type signatures. In the low magnetic image more amorphous low magnetic anomalies tend to outline the interior periphery of the house platforms. These results are discussed in greater detail below.

Figures A4 and **A5** show the corresponding conductivity and magnetic susceptibility for portions of houses 1, 3 and 5 in area of interest that were identified in the gradiometry data. During the magnetic interpretations, anomalies identified in the magnetic data were broken into three categories; negative, positive, and dipolar. Based on their geographical location on the site, the anomalies were further broken down into interior or exterior to the house platform as seen by the topography (**Figure A6**).

House 1 Grid

House 1 is the most northern structure and lowest in elevation. It is located just south of a modern fence and close to the beach where the flat plank house depression is readily accessible to boaters. Due to its location and ease of access, metal debris (trash) was evident along the eastern edge of the house depression during the survey. Despite efforts to remove the trash, multiple magnetic dipolar anomalies are present in the data that also show up as higher values in the conductivity and magnetic susceptibility images.

Because the area surveyed for House 1 is almost entirely interior to the house depression there is little distinguished in the interpretive map other than high, low, or dipolar magnetic anomalies. Overall, there are several high magnetic anomalies in House 1 that could represent archaeological features.

Houses 3, 4 and 5 Grid

House 3 is the largest (longest E-W) house depression topographically visible at the site. It is situated upslope and south from both House 1 and House 2 (not surveyed during this project). It is also north of Houses 4 and 5 and the topography indicates that it is the length of Houses 4 and 5 combined. Houses 3, 4 and 5 were surveyed in as one continuous grid system which allows a greater opportunity to identify patterns relating to the archaeology in the magnetic data.

Anomalies found to be of interest include those represented as interior higher magnetism flanked by interior low anomalies particularly to the north and south. In House 3 a more pronounced band of low magnetic anomalies seem to appear along the southern edge (considered the back of the house as the platform is dug into the slope). In general those areas with higher magnetic features within the house depression may represent heavily utilized areas (as opposed to the low magnetic peripheral areas). Those higher magnetic anomalies form a structured band across the center of the depression. These are consistent with signatures of hearths, fired clay, pits, or large post-holes filled in with magnetically rich soil. Hearths from this site and similar sites tend to be large amorphous features that have been used and reused through extended periods of times. While the interior features in these houses seem rather discrete, they may also represent the most recent firing event of an overall larger and longer-used hearth system.

Previously excavated test units consistently appear as negative anomalies in houses 3-5 unless a metal nail still remained, in which case there is as a strong dipolar anomaly. Areas between the houses tend to have higher magnetism making the difference between houses even more distinct (see **Figure A6**). The negative values near the edges of the house are likely due to top soils being removed during construction and placed outside between the houses; those displaced upper soils generally resulting in higher magnetism. These peripheral interior spaces remain relatively less altered than the central interior areas where more intense activities were likely occurring including fire use.

House 4 is a depression located to the southeast. The easternmost portion of the house was not surveyed due to dense vegetation. While House 4 is not as clearly distinct as House 3 in magnetic anomaly strength, the lower strength spatial patterning is consistent with the signature of House 3: Interior high magnetic anomalies are separated by a low outer peripheral group of anomalies as highlighted in **Figure A6**.

To the southwest is the depression of House 5. This house has been subject to several test excavations. One recent excavation tested a GPR anomaly interpreted as a hearth. The magnetic survey did not identify any anomalies consistent with a hearth. It is possible that ground disturbance from the adjacent test unit may have caused enough disturbance to make the signal unidentifiable. Additionally, thorough cleaning of the hearth in combination with its depth below the modern ground surface could also account for its undetectable signature, especially given the relatively naturally high magnetism of soils in the area. This house also exhibits a similar spatial pattern to Houses 3 and 4 with interior high anomalies surrounded by peripheral low anomalies within the depression. However, the distinction is less clear.

Grid 1

The intent of the Grid 1 survey area was to collect data exterior to the house platforms and compare it with GPR data that was collected over the same area. The majority of work during this project was focused on house interiors. Data for this Grid show variations in magnetics, but no distinct patterns appear in the data. A comparison to the GPR data is needed to determine if interesting anomalies appear a larger area of survey should be surveyed.

CONCLUSIONS

Archaeological geophysics like other remote sensing methods, including aerial photo interpretation, satellite image and lidar analyses, generally relies on large, contiguous survey areas to successfully identify the regular, geometric shapes that indicate the presence of cultural features. Because these characteristics do not commonly occur in nature, this phenomenon serves as a fundamental recognition element in all archaeological remote sensing (Avery and Berlin 1992). The site of Dinisio Point is located in a region in which such an approach is made difficult, if not impossible by the dense standing and decomposing vegetation that characterizes the Pacific Northwest. Perhaps it is due to this challenging environment that archaeo-geophysics is not a commonly employed survey methodology in the region. This particular survey was made more challenging by steep slopes that were extremely difficult and frequently impossible to traverse. It was these conditions that limited survey size resulted in numerous omissions in the data. However, this did not preclude the success of these efforts in making useful contributions to the study interior and exterior organization of these plank houses.

The numerous high magnetic anomalies identified in the interior house spaces reveal spatial patterns and extents of potential hearths or post holes that would have otherwise taken months or years to reveal through excavation. More amorphous high and low anomalies characterize general areas of the houses' interior and exterior spaces. While these methods cannot and do not replace the utility and detail that can be obtained through careful excavation, they do serve as a valuable line of evidence to guide future investigations. Further analyses of these findings in combination with excavation records could serve to further define the magnetic signatures of plank houses and their associated features in a way that would allow for even smaller surveys to positively identify portions of these archeological components.

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Appendix A
Geophysical Results Maps

**Figure A1. Dionisio Point Site
(DgRv-3) Gradiometry Data.**

House 1

Grid 1

**Figure A2. Dionisio Point Site
(DgRv-3) Isolated Positive
Magnetic Data.**

House 1

Grid 1

**Figure A3. Dionisio Point Site
(DgRv-3) Isolated Negative
Magnetic Data.**

House 1

Grid 1

Figure A4. Dionisio Point Site (DgRv-3)
Magnetic Gradiometry (nT) and
Conductivity (mS/m).

House 1

154N, 154.6E

Grid 1

124N, 150E

Figure A5. Dionisio Point Site (DgRv-3)
Magnetic Gradiometry (nT)
and Susceptibility (ppt).

House 1

Grid 1

**Figure A6. Dionisio Point Site
(DgRv-3) Gradiometry Interpretations.**

 Dipole

0 2.75 5.5 11 Meters

**Figure A7. Dionisio Point Site
(DgRv-3) Gradiometry Data.**

House 1

Figure A8. Dionisio Point Site (DgRv-3).

- Legend**
- Tree
 - ▨ Excavation units
 - ▬ Logs
 - Fence
 - ▨ Modern trash
 - Contour (Interval = 1 m)

0 2.5 5 10 Meters

House 1

Grid 1

House 3

House 4

House 5

Down slope

